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tial. In this communication, we report the isolation, identification and relative occurrence of these amino acids.

The aerial parts of the plant, *S. paniculata* were collected from Khayerpur area of greater Agartala in September, 1985. The air-dried milled aerial parts (1 kg) were extracted with petrol (b.p. 60–80°) and 90% ethanol successively in a Soxhlet for 48 h each. The alcoholic extract was concentrated to gummy residue (30.5 g). Chromatography^{3,4} of a part of the residue (1.5 g) through Amberlite 1R 120(H) and elution of the column for basic amino acids with 2 N aqueous HCl as described⁵, led to the identification of lysine, glycine and proline by co-pc with authentic samples.

Another portion of the crude residue (1.5 g) was chromatographed through Amberlite IRA 400 (OH) and elution of the column with 2 N acetic acid for neutral and acidic amino acids, led to the identification of histidine, glutamic acid, hydroxyproline, proline, alanine, methionine, threonine, tyrosine, valine and leucine by co-pc with authentic samples. Proline was also found from the column of cation-exchange resin.

All these amino acids from their mixture were isolated as their ninhydrin complexes by preparative pc⁶ on Whatmann no. 3 mm using solvent-1 as developing solvent and their relative occurrence in μg per g of the air-dried aerial parts estimated colorimetrically⁵ was found to be alanine, 3.20; lysine, 2.75; threonine, 2.40; methionine, 1.68; leucine, 1.54; valine, 1.52; proline, 1.33; hydroxyproline, 1.31; tyrosine, 1.30; histidine, 0.50; glutamic acid, 0.39 and glycine, 0.03. This is the first report of the amino acid composition from the genus, *Spilanthes*.

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Selective Separations of Mercury(II) from various Divalent Metal Ions by Extraction from Mercury(II)-Phenanthroline-Rose Bengal Ternary Systems

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1, 10-phenanthroline and its derivatives react with many divalent metal ions to form stable cationic complexes which can be extracted with non-coordinating anionic dyes as ion-pair systems. These systems due to their high molar absorptivity have been extensively investigated by several workers. Rose Bengal extra (tetrachloro-tetraiodofluorescein), erythrocyne (tetraiodofluorescein), eosin (tetrabromofluorescein) were used as anionic counter ions for the extraction of cationic complexes of Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Pb^{2+} with 1,10-phenanthroline which yield intensely coloured extracts in chloroform and ethyl acetate. The molar absorptivity in each case is greater than the corresponding metal dithizonate. We have earlier reported the effect of solvent on the nature of extracting species in the case of Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ternary systems with 1,10-phenanthroline and Rose Bengal.

In our investigations on the extraction of Hg^{2+} with 1,10-phenanthroline and Rose Bengal, surprisingly we have observed that extraction of Hg^{2+} is completely inhibited by the excess presence of Rose Bengal, whereas many divalent metal ions can be quantitatively extracted under these conditions. Based on these results, a procedure for the selective separation of Hg^{2+} from diverse metal ions has been developed and these results are presented in this communication.

Experimental

Extraction procedure: To an aliquot of Hg^{2+} solution (containing 100 μg Hg) in a 125 ml separatory funnel, solutions of 1×10^{-3} M 1,10-phenanthroline (2.5 ml) and 1×10^{-4} M Rose Bengal (5 ml) were added. The pH was adjusted to 8.5 by adding dilute NaOH and made volume upto 20 ml with distilled water. The solution was shaken with chloroform (20 ml) for 5 min. After separation of the two phases, the organic phase was removed and its absorbance measured at 560 nm against reagent blank. To determine the percentage extraction of Hg^{2+} under different conditions, the organic phase was back-extracted with 0.1 N H_2SO_4 and Hg^{2+} was then determined by Hg-dithizone method.

Results and Discussion

It is observed that Hg^{II}-phenanthroline-Rose Bengal system can be extracted into chloroform and nitrobenzene giving a pink extract with λ_{max} at 560 nm (ε=3.3×10⁴ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) which can be best extracted in the pH range 8-9. A forty-fold of 1,10-phenanthroline and equal concentration of Rose Bengal to that of Hg^{II} yielded maximum absorbance for the ternary system.

It has been observed that initially the extraction of the ternary system increases with the increasing concentration of Rose Bengal upto a mole ratio of 1 : 1, while in the region 1 to 3.5 times of Rose Bengal to mercury, the extraction of Hg^{II} shows a definite decreasing trend which finally becomes zero with four-fold excess of the dye. This has been confirmed with two different concentrations of Hg^{II} which is most likely due to the replacement of 1,10-phenanthroline from coordination by the dye resulting in the formation of anionic complex. However, in the case of Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, Mn^{II} and Pb^{II} a 50-fold excess of both 1,10 phenanthroline and Rose Bengal are found to be sufficient to achieve complete extraction of these corresponding ion-pairs and any further excess of the dye even upto 200-fold does not change their extraction behaviour. The extraction behaviour of various ternary systems with different divalent metal ions along with Hg^{II}-phen-RB system in the

pH range 5-9 in presence of excess of the reagents is shown in Fig. 1, which reveals that it can be used for an efficient separation technique for Hg^{II} from other metal ions. The separation factors for various metals are given in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Extraction of various divalent metals of ion-pairs in presence of 1,10-phenanthroline and excess of Rose Bengal at different pH values into chloroform : (...) Ni, (○) Zn, (●) Cd, (⊗) Cu, (■) Mn, and (□) Hg.

TABLE 1—SEPARATION AND ESTIMATION OF MERCURY(II) IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Sl. no.	Composition μg	Recovery of mercury* %	Recovery of added ions* %	Average separation factor β
1.	Hg ^{II} + Zn ^{II}			5.553 × 10 ³
	50 : 50	98.6	98.3	
	80 : 50	98.4	99.0	
2.	Hg ^{II} + Cd ^{II}			4.810 × 10 ³
	50 : 50	98.8	98.7	
	80 : 50	98.3	98.4	
3.	Hg ^{II} + Ni ^{II}			5.393 × 10 ³
	50 : 50	98.9	98.5	
	80 : 50	98.3	98.9	
4.	Hg ^{II} + Cu ^{II}			4.596 × 10 ³
	50 : 50	98.3	98.5	
	80 : 50	98.7	99.0	
5.	Hg ^{II} + Mn ^{II}			5.251 × 10 ³
	50 : 50	98.3	98.9	
	80 : 50	98.5	98.2	
6.	Hg ^{II} + Co ^{II}			5.010 × 10 ³
	50 : 50	98.6	99.9	
	80 : 50	93.2	97.0	
7.	Hg ^{II} + Pb ^{II}			5.751 × 10 ³
	50 : 50	99.5	96.2	
	80 : 50	98.5	98.8	
8.	Hg ^{II} + Zn ^{II} + Cd ^{II}			—
	15 : 200 : 200	98.7	99.6	
	50 : 50	99.33	—	
9.	Hg ^{II} + Co ^{II} + Ni ^{II} + Mn ^{II}			—
	15 : 200 : 200 : 200	98.67	—	
	50 : 50 : 50 : 50	99.00	—	
10.	Hg ^{II} + Pb ^{II} + Cd ^{II} + Cu ^{II}			—
	15 : 200 : 200 : 200	99.00	—	
	50 : 50 : 50 : 50	—	—	

*Average of three determinations.

Procedure for the separation of Hg^{2+} from various divalent metal ions: To the synthetic mixture containing Hg^{2+} and various divalent metal ions taken in a 125 ml separatory funnel, add $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ phenanthroline (5 ml), $1 \times 10^{-1} M$ Rose Bengal (5 ml) were added and pH was adjusted to 8.5 by adding dilute NaOH and made upto 20 ml with distilled water. Then the solution was equilibrated with chloroform (20 ml) for 5 min on a mechanical shaker and the organic phase removed. The extraction process was repeated with fresh aliquots of chloroform (2×20 ml) and all the organic phases and aqueous phases were collected separately (in this process, all other divalent metal ions go into organic phase as $[Metal : (phen)_2]^{2+} : RB^{2-}$ ion-pairs, while Hg^{2+} remains in aqueous phase as $1 : 2 [Hg : 2RB]^{2-}$ anionic complex). pH of the aqueous phase was adjusted to 1.5 by adding dilute H_2SO_4 . This solution was equilibrated again with chloroform (20 ml) for 5 min on a mechanical shaker to remove completely the excess of Rose Bengal. Then Hg^{2+} present in the aqueous phase was estimated by Hg^{2+} -dithizone method.

Several synthetic mixtures containing Hg^{2+} and diverse ions were analysed by the same procedure and the corresponding results are given in Table 1. It can be seen that the present method offers efficient procedure for the separation of Hg^{2+} from various divalent metal ions, like Zn, Cd, Cu, Mn, Ni, Co and Pb, with an average separation factor (for a single extraction process) about 5.2×10^3 . For achieving still better separation, multiple stage extractions should be employed. The composition of the extracting species is found to be 1 : 1 : 1 for the Hg^{2+} -phen-RB from log D vs pA plots^{10,11}, where D is the distribution of Hg^{2+} at different reagent concentrations in between aqueous and organic phases and A is the reagent concentration.

The decrease in the extraction of Hg^{2+} with increasing Rose Bengal concentration can be explained as follows. Due to high affinity of iodo group to Hg^{2+} . Rose Bengal molecule enters into coordination with Hg^{2+} and forms a stronger complex than phenanthroline does with Hg^{2+} .

$Hg^{2+} + Phen + Rose Bengal \rightarrow$

Species A + Excess of Rose Bengal $\rightarrow$

When the mole fraction of Rose Bengal is just equal to or less than that of Hg^{2+} , the ternary complex (species A) is formed which is extractable quantitatively. However, as the concentration of Rose Bengal is increased it even replaces phenanthroline from coordination because of its high affinity to Hg^{2+} forming an unextractable anionic complex (species B), which has been utilised for the selective separation of Hg^{2+} from other divalent metal ions.

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